

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“LESSONS FROM A ROSE”

Your love shines through my cloudy day,
Your smile warms my heart from lonely gray,
Hearing your voice cradles my soul,
As you crack some jokes making my day whole.

Our candy might be sweet and sour,
Yet day by day it blooms into flower.
I hope it grows, but nobody knows
When a plant turns into a rose.

Three years passed, but you weren't here all along
It did last, but not for long,
The rose it pricked and scarred me deep,
You turned away - no words to keep.
No trace of guilt, no soft apology,
Can't forget how you are not sorry.

What happened it happened,
Heart feels, the silence fasten
No longer looking for that sincerity
Time heals and my mind in clarity.

Lesson to take and notes to make,
Thank the Creator for each heartbreak
It leads to where my soul wants to be,
To where I'm truly meant to be.